

An individually tailored self-management app-based intervention (SELFBACK) versus a self-management web-based intervention (e-Help) or usual care in people with low back and neck pain referred to secondary care: protocol for a multi-arm randomised clinical trial

Section 1: Administrative Information

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This SAP is based on the protocol registered in ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT04463043) and the submitted protocol paper. The structure and content of the SAP is adopted from the Guidelines for the Content of Statistical Analyses Plans in Clinical Trials ¹.

Table 1. SAP revision history

Revision	Justification for revision	Version (date)

Signatures

Senior Statistician

Project Coordinator

Section 2: Introduction

2.1 Background and rationale

Self-management is a key element in the care of low back pain (LBP) and neck pain (NP). Current best evidence recommends that self-management is tailored to individual needs and capabilities and includes elements such as education, exercise programs, and advice to stay active². In primary care, general practitioners commonly lack time, resources and training for delivering evidence-based self-management support³, while access to specialist care for patients with more complex symptoms is generally limited and requires long waiting time. Digital solutions, such as mobile applications (apps) provide a viable option for supporting tailored self-management across care pathways as they can be accessible to patients at any time and at low cost. The role of digital interventions as an adjunct to secondary care have not yet been explored. Further, the added benefit of a tailored over a non-tailored approach is currently unclear.

We have developed an evidence-based and data-driven decision support system (DSS) delivered via a smartphone app – SELFBACK – to facilitate, improve and reinforce individually tailored self-management of non-specific LBP, which has been adapted to also target NP⁴. Additionally, we have developed a website – eHelp – that mimics the content of the SELFBACK app, but without individual tailoring. The effectiveness of these digital interventions is evaluated in a secondary care setting in a multi-arm randomised clinical trial (RCT).

2.2 Objectives

The primary objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of the SELFBACK DSS as adjunct to usual care versus usual care only. The secondary objective is to compare the effectiveness of the SELFBACK DSS to the e-Help website as well as e-Help vs usual care. The primary outcome is musculoskeletal health at three months measured by the Musculoskeletal Pain Questionnaire (MSK-HQ).

The effect of the interventions on secondary outcomes, including quality of life, use of non-prescriptive medication, sleep problems, depressive symptoms, stress, functional ability, and pain intensity, will be assessed at three months. We will also evaluate the effect on these measures, as well as on MSK-HQ, at six months.

Section 3: Study Methods

3.1 Trial design

This study is designed as a multi-arm RCT where patients with LBP and/or NP are randomised to three parallel groups (allocation ratio 1:1:1). The intervention groups will be given access to the SELFBACK DSS delivered via a smartphone app, or to the e-Help website, additional to usual care, whereas the control group will get usual care only. The target population is people referred to secondary care for LBP and/or NP at the multidisciplinary clinic for back-, neck-, and shoulder rehabilitation at St. Olavs Hospital, Trondheim, Norway; see also sections 5.2 and 5.3.

3.2 Randomization

Randomisation is performed as a permuted block randomisation of random size unknown to the research team to ensure allocation concealment. Randomisation is performed by a web-based randomisation system (Web Case Report Form; WebCRF) developed and administered by Unit of Applied Clinical Research, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, NTNU, Trondheim, Norway. This unit is not otherwise involved in the trial management or trial conduct.

3.3 Sample size

The sample size calculation is described in detail in the registered protocol. Briefly, the study aims to detect a four-point difference between the intervention groups, i.e. SELFBACK and e-Help and the control group in musculoskeletal health measured by the MSK-HQ at three months follow-up. Using the *sampsi* procedure within Stata, assuming a standard deviation of the MSK-HQ score of 10 points and a correlation between repeated measures of 0.4 and a 30% drop-out, a sample size of at least 279 participants (93 in each arm) will be included in this trial.

3.4 Framework

This trial is designed as a superiority RCT assessing the effectiveness of digital interventions (i.e., the SELFBACK DSS or the e-Help website) in addition to usual care, compared to usual care only (control group) for people with LBP and/or NP. Three comparisons will be performed, SELFBACK vs usual care (primary analysis), e-Help vs usual care and SELFBACK vs e-Help (secondary analyses).

3.5 Interim analyses and stopping guidance

As serious adverse events are unexpected, no interim analysis or a priori defined stopping rules are defined or implemented for this trial.

3.6 Timing of outcome assessment

The primary and secondary outcome variables will be assessed at baseline and at six weeks, three months, and six months follow-up. This allows analyses of repeated measures on both primary and secondary outcomes, and thus increased statistical power compared to outcomes assessed at a single time-point.

3.7 Timing of final analyses

The analyses of the primary outcome will be conducted within three months after the last participant has completed the six months follow-up questionnaire. The inclusion of participants continued until April 2021, and thus the final analyses should be ready by end of January 2022. Analyses of secondary outcomes assessed at three and six months will be analysed subsequently to the primary outcome and conducted within the same time frame.

Section 4: Statistical Principles

4.1 Confidence intervals and P-values

As recently recommended in the medical literature, we will not use a specific *P*-value threshold to decide upon statistical significance as this often leads to misinterpretation of results. For the same reasons, we will not adjust for multiple comparisons since this build upon a strict use of a certain *P*-value threshold. Instead, the precision of the estimated effects of the intervention will be assessed by a 95% confidence interval, and the effect will be described as a point estimate (mean difference or odds ratio/relative risk) with accompanying confidence limits. Whenever *P*-values are reported, we will do so by presenting their actual value, and not reduce them to a binary inequality under or above a threshold value.

4.2 Adherence and protocol deviations

The first login to the SELFBACK app and e-Help website will be monitored to check if participants accessed the allocated intervention. Participants who do not access the intervention after the reminders or want to discontinue its use will be followed up as usual. Data analytics on usage and interaction with the app/web interventions will be available as an indirect measure of adherence. There is currently no optimal way to measure adherence in self-management interventions⁵⁻⁷ which makes it challenging to establish a per-protocol analysis. Additionally, there is a risk that a per-protocol analysis can be biased if participants who engage with the digital intervention have different prognosis from those who engage less with it. As such, the primary analysis will include all participants enrolled in the study (see 4.3 for details), but we will conduct supplementary exploratory analyses in subgroups according to different definitions of adherence: 1) restricted to participants who have accessed the app or web page; and 2) have had a certain level of engagement with the SELFBACK app, e.g. having generated six self-management plans during the first twelve weeks after enrolment.

4.3 Analysis populations

The main effect of the intervention will be analysed according to the intention-to-treat principle using linear mixed models for continuous outcomes and generalized estimated equations (GEE) for binary outcomes (logistic and Poisson models), and the analyses will include all participants initially enrolled in the study and who answered the baseline questionnaire and were randomised. The web-based baseline questionnaire does not allow participants to proceed without filling in an answer, so there will be no missing data at this time point. A similar solution will be used for the follow-up questionnaires, but missing data will be generated if participants do not answer the follow-up questionnaire (i.e. due to withdrawal or loss to follow-up).

Any missing values throughout the follow-up period are inherently accounted for in the mixed model approach and complete case analysis will be applied in sensitivity analyses (see chapter 6.2 and 6.3 below for further details). A complete case will be defined as a participant who has answered both the baseline and the three-month questionnaire. We will also conduct supplementary exploratory analyses only including participants from the intervention arm who are defined as adhering to the intervention (see chapter 4.2 for more details).

Section 5: Trial Population

5.1 Screening data

The trial does not aim to collect any screening data to describe the representativeness of the sample.

5.2 Eligibility

Detailed inclusion and exclusion criteria are described in the registered protocol. Briefly, participants must be ≥ 18 years, referred and accepted to a secondary care hospital outpatient clinic for LBP and/or NP and own a smartphone with internet access. Participants are excluded if they have 'red flags' indicating possible serious pathology, if they are unable to take part in exercise of physical activity or unable to speak and/or read Norwegian.

5.3 Recruitment

The recruitment of participants is conducted in Trondheim at the multidisciplinary outpatient clinic for back-, neck-, and shoulder rehabilitation at St. Olavs Hospital. The recruitment was conducted between July 2020 and April 2021 and details about the number of participants contacted and included in the trial will be visualised in the CONSORT flow-chart.

5.4 Withdrawal and follow-up

Each participant is informed that they can withdraw from the study at any time, and that they then have the right to have any personal, health and questionnaire data deleted. If a participant withdraws during the follow-up period, but do not require already collected data to be deleted, the data will be used in the analyses until the time point for withdrawal. For analyses of the primary and secondary outcomes at three months, loss to follow-up is defined as not answering the three-month questionnaire. Loss-to-follow-up will be assessed for each outcome variable separately. The same principle to define loss-to-follow-up will be used for the six-month follow-up time point. The number of participants providing information at each follow-up time point will be visualised in the CONSORT flow-chart, and this also displays the number who withdrew or were lost to follow-up between each follow-up time-point.

5.5. Baseline patient characteristics

Eligible participants fill in a baseline web questionnaire after consenting to take part in the study. Baseline characteristics that are collected include: age, sex, height, weight, housing (live alone or with family), education, employment, work characteristics, physical activity, sleep problems, mental health, stress, quality of life, and various pain-related factors (e.g., localisation, duration, intensity, coping, disability and limitations, perceptions and beliefs). Depending on the nature of the variables, we will summarise this information in a baseline table showing mean values with standard deviation or numbers and percentages within the three trial arms. We will not conduct any statistical tests of baseline differences, as this violates the assumptions for the randomisation procedure.

Section 6: Analyses

6.1 Outcome definitions

All outcome variables described below are assessed at baseline, six weeks, three, and six months. The primary follow-up time point is three months, both for the primary and secondary outcome variables described below. For each follow-up period, all measures will inform the analyses (e.g. baseline, six-week and six-month data will be included when analysing effects at three months).

Primary outcome variable

The primary outcome is the mean difference in musculoskeletal health assessed at three months from baseline, measured by the MSK-HQ⁸. The questionnaire contains 14 items assessing severity of pain/stiffness, physical function, physical activity level, symptoms interference, sleep, fatigue, emotional health, understanding of the condition, confidence to self-manage, independence and overall impact of symptoms. Each item is scored from 0 to 4 and are summed to provide a final score (range 0-56), with higher scores indicating better musculoskeletal health. The main analyses will be based on the raw scores, and we will estimate mean group differences in MSK-HQ at three months using a linear mixed model for repeated measures. We will also construct a binary variable representing a clinically meaningful change in MSK-HQ of four points or more during the three months follow-up period that will be analysed using a Poisson GEE analyses for repeated measures to estimate relative risks.

Secondary outcome variables

- *The Roland Morris Disability Questionnaire (RMDQ)* will be used to assess pain-related disability⁹. The RMDQ includes 24 items asking participants to indicate if they experience functional impairments by answering “yes” or “no” to a series of descriptions of functional abilities. The RMDQ score ranges from 0 to 24, where a higher score indicates higher levels of pain-related disability. We will compare mean group differences in RMDQ using a linear mixed model for repeated measures. There is no consensus on what constitute a clinically meaningful improvement on RMDQ, i.e., this may vary from two to four points¹⁰⁻¹³. We will construct a binary variable representing a clinically meaningful change in RMDQ defined as four points.
- *Neck Disability Index (NDI)* will be used to assess neck-specific disability¹⁴. The questionnaire has 10 items regarding pain and activities of daily living including personal care, lifting, reading, headaches, concentration, work status, driving, sleeping and recreation. The NDI score ranges from 0 to 50 with higher scores indicating greater disability. We will compare mean group differences in NDI using a linear mixed model for repeated measures. Although it is not clear what constitutes a clinically meaningful improvement on NDI^{14 15} we will construct a binary variable using 7.5 points as cut-off value.
- *Pain intensity* over the past week will be assessed by asking “Please indicate your average/worst low back and/or neck pain level during the last week“, using an 11-point numerical rating scale (NRS) ranging from “0 (zero)” to “10”¹⁶. We will compare mean group differences in pain intensity using linear mixed models. We will also construct a binary variable to indicate moderate/severe pain (>5 points).
- *Health-related quality of life* is evaluated with the EuroQoL 5-dimension (EQ-5D) questionnaire¹⁷. A 5-point Likert scale ranging from “1 [no problems]” to “5 [complete inability]” is used to assess the health-related quality of life within each of

the five dimensions (i.e., mobility, self-care, activities, pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression). We will construct an overall weighted index based on a value set that combines all items and then estimate the mean difference between groups using linear mixed models.

- *General health* is assessed on a 100-point vertical scale where 0 indicates the worst health you can imagine and 100 the best imaginable health¹⁷. The variable will be analysed as a continuous variable estimating the mean difference between groups using linear mixed models.
- *The Pain Self-Efficacy Questionnaire* (PSEQ) assesses the participant's level of confidence in carrying out specific activities despite their pain¹⁸. The PSEQ is a 10-item questionnaire scored on an ordinal scale ranging from "zero [completely disagree]" to "six [completely agree]". A total score is calculated by summing the scores for each of the 10 items, yielding a maximum total score of 60, where higher scores reflect stronger self-efficacy beliefs. We will compare mean group differences in PSEQ using linear mixed models. We will also construct a binary variable to indicate low and high self-efficacy using a cut-off value of 40.
- *The Brief Illness Perception Questionnaire* (BIPQ) evaluates the participants' illness perception in an 8-item questionnaire¹⁹. Items are scored on an ordinal scale ranging from "0 [no problems]" to "10 [worst severity]". Adding the separate score values creates a summary score with a higher score indicating more threatening view of the pain. The summed score will be analysed as a continuous variable to compare mean group differences, and we will also construct a binary variable with cut-offs indicated from the distribution of the variable (e.g. percentiles) since no clinical cut offs are suggested in the literature.
- *The Fear-Avoidance Belief Questionnaire* (FABQ) assesses participant's beliefs about how physical activity and work affect their pain²⁰. The FABQ is a 5-item questionnaire, where the participants score their beliefs about their pain on an ordinal scale ranging from "zero [completely disagree]" to "six [completely agree]". The four latter questions will be summed (range 0-24) to represent fear avoidance beliefs about physical activity and analysed as a continuous variable to compare mean group differences using linear mixed models. We will also classify people as having high or low fear for physical activity to examine possible differences in a binary variable. The classification cut-off will be obtained from the distribution of the variable (i.e., median value).
- *Stress* is evaluated with the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), a 10-item questionnaire asking about frequency of thoughts and feelings related to perceived stress²¹. Participants indicate their frequency of experiencing stress-related issues on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "0 [never]" to "4 [very often]". Positive score items are reversed and then all items are summed to a score ranging from 0 to 40. The resulting sum score will be analysed as a continuous variable to estimate mean differences in stress using linear mixed models. A score ≥ 27 is considered high stress and will be used as cut-off value to construct a binary variable.
- *The Patient Health Questionnaire-8* (PHQ-8) is an 8-item questionnaire used to evaluate the participants' depressive symptoms²². Items are reported on a 4-point Likert scale scoring frequency of experiencing symptoms of depression. The nine items will be summed and analysed both as a continuous variable using linear mixed models and as a binary variable using a cut-off 15 to classify people into none/mild/moderate versus moderately severe/severe depression.
- *Function* is evaluated by the Patient Specific Functional Scale (PSFS) where participants are asked to rate up to two self-selected activities they are unable to do or

having difficulties performing²³. The ability to carry out the activity/activities is rated from “zero [unable to perform]” to “10 [fully able to perform]”. We will compare mean difference in function using linear mixed models.

- *Self-reported physical activity* is evaluated by the Modernised Saltin-Grimby Physical Activity Level Scale, where participants indicate their amount of time per week performing leisure activities with four levels of intensity ranging from sedentary to vigorous physically active²⁴. The resulting four categories will be analysed as a binary variable indicating no/light activity vs moderate/vigorous activity.
- *Sleep problems* is assessed by four items including problems with falling asleep, waking up repeatedly, waking up too early, and feeling sleepy during the day²⁵. Response options for each item are “seldom or never”, “sometimes” or “several times a week”. The information retrieved from these four items approximates the information necessary to diagnose insomnia according to the DSM-V criteria, and will be analysed as a binary variable (insomnia vs no insomnia).
- *Work ability* is measured by a single-item on current work ability rated on an 11-point NRS scale ranging from “zero [completely unable to work]” to “10 [work ability at its best]”²⁶. We will compare mean difference in work ability using linear mixed models. We will also classify people into a binary variable representing high (>7 points) vs low work ability.
- *Patient Acceptable Symptom State* is a single item question: “Considering your pain, do you consider your current state satisfactory?” with response options yes or no²⁷. This will be analysed as a binary variable.
- *Patient’s Global Perceived Effect* is a single item question where participants are asked to rate improvement or deterioration of their pain status compared to before the intervention with seven response options ranging from -5 [markedly worse] to 5 [markedly better]²⁸. The variable will be analysed as a binary variable indicating improved vs not improved.
- *Pain medication* is collected by the question “How many days during the last week have you taken non-prescription pain medication for your pain?” with four response options ranging from “never” to “daily”. Although this information is collected at follow-up the variable will not be included as a secondary outcome.
- *Long term pain duration* is measured by “What is the total length of time that you have had low back or neck trouble during the last 12 months?” with five response options ranging from “0 days” to “every day”. Although this information is collected at follow-up the variable will not be included as a secondary outcome.

6.2 Analyses methods

The primary analysis will estimate mean difference and 95% confidence interval (CI) in MSK-HQ score at three months follow-up between the intervention and control group (i.e., SELFBACK in addition to usual care versus usual care only). The analyses will be conducted according to the intention-to-treat principle using a linear mixed model for repeated measures. This model includes all available data for all participants at each time point (i.e. baseline, six weeks, and three months). The distribution of the MSK-HQ score will be assessed, and the variable may be transformed (e.g. log transformation) to better fit with the assumptions for the regression analyses. In the regression model, individual participants will be specified as a random effect, accounting for the within subject covariance structure. The effect of group and time will be specified as fixed effects using a joint variable of

intervention and time in a constrained longitudinal data analysis approach. Here, baseline levels are pooled over the two study groups assuming that any baseline differences are due to chance; this also controls for any baseline differences in the outcome variable. The same approach will be used for the other two comparisons, i.e. e-Help website vs usual care and SELFBACK vs e-Help website.

All analyses will include adjustment for baseline levels of potentially important prognostic factors, such as age, sex, socioeconomic status, and pain intensity. We will also use Poisson GEE analyses to estimate relative risk (with 95% CI) for a four-point change in MSK-HQ between the groups taking into account the repeated observations. This analysis will be adjusted for the same factors as those included in the linear mixed model.

To reduce the risk of biased interpretation of results for the primary outcome we will draft separate interpretations based on the results from the main analyses, with groups arbitrarily labelled as A, B, and C (Table 2). After agreeing on the interpretations, the randomisation code is broken, and the correct interpretation will be used.

Table 2. An interpretation will be drafted for each of the six possible combinations of group labelling before unblinding the group allocation.

Label	Interpret. 1	Interpret. 2	Interpret. 3	Interpret. 4	Interpret. 5	Interpret. 6
A	SELFBACK	SELFBACK	e-Help	e-Help	Control	Control
B	e-Help	Control	SELFBACK	Control	e-Help	SELFBACK
C	Control	e-Help	Control	SELFBACK	SELFBACK	e-Help

In addition to the intention to treat analyses, we will conduct supplementary exploratory per protocol analyses using information on adherence to the trial as described in chapter 4.2 above.

All secondary outcomes will be analysed using the same approach as described for the primary outcome; linear mixed models will be used to estimate mean differences between groups in continuous variables, and for binary variables we will use Poisson GEE analyses to estimate relative risk. Pre-specified cut-offs for binary variables are described in 6.1 above. For analyses of mean differences, the distribution of each outcome variable will be assessed to inform possible transformation or initiate alternative analytical procedures (e.g. non-parametric analyses). The precision of all estimated effects will be assessed by a 95% CI.

Possible modifiers of the effect of intervention on the primary outcome will be assessed in supplementary analyses stratified by sex, age groups, socioeconomic status and different levels of pain severity etc., and accompanied by tests of statistical interaction to assess departure from additive effects (i.e., including a product term of group and modifier in the regression model).

6.3 Missing data

Any missing values are inherently accounted for in the mixed model/GEE approach assuming that the data are missing at random. We will also conduct complete case analyses including people with data on all time-points.

6.4 Additional analyses

Additional analyses include exploratory analyses, analyses of secondary outcomes, analyses stratified by possible effect modifiers, analyses using multiple imputation of missing data and complete case analyses. These analyses are described above in chapter 6.1-6.3.

6.5 Harms

Since no harms are expected, we do not plan any specific analyses for this. If any study related harms should occur, these will be described and reported.

6.6 Statistical software

All analyses related to the primary outcome will be conducted using Stata.

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